

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

Grant Agreement No. 870626

Deliverable Title	Periodic project report
Periodic report no:	1
Period covered by the report:	01/01/2020-30/06/2021
Deliverable Lead:	SSSA
Partner(s) involved:	All
Related Work Package:	WP1 – Management and coordination
Related Task/Subtask:	T1.1 Project coordination
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Contributors:	Task leaders, Partners’ team members
Dissemination Level:	Public
Due Delivery Date:	31.12.2021
Actual Delivery:	04.01.2022
Project ID	870626
Instrument:	H2020-SC6-GOVERNANCE-2019
Start Date of Project:	01.01.2020
Duration:	36 months

Version history table			
Version	Date	Modification reason	Modifier(s)
v.01	14.12.2021	First draft	Alma Serica
v.02	22.12.2021	Revised draft	WP leaders
v.03	04.01.2021	Final version	Caterina Sganga

Table of contents

Abbreviations List	4
List of tables.....	5
List of figures	5
1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress	6
1.1. Objectives' status M1-M18.....	8
1.2 Explanation of the work carried per WP in M1-M18.....	17
1.2.1 Work Package 1 – Management and Coordination [M1-M36; WP Leader: SSSA].....	21
1.2.2 Work Package 2 – End users and access to culture [M1-M36; WP Leader: SSSA].....	23
1.2.3 Work Package 3 – Authors and performers [M1-M28; WP Leader: UvA-IViR]	26
1.2.4 Work Package 4 – Creative industries [M1-M36; WP Leader: UGLA-CREATe]	28
1.2.5 Work Package 5 – Galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) [M1-M36; WP Leader: UNITN].	30
1.2.6 Work Package 6 – Intermediaries (Copyright Content Moderation and Removal at Scale in the Digital Single Market: What Impact on Access to Culture?) [M1-M33; WP Leader: UvA-IViR]	32
1.2.7 Work Package 7 – Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach [M1-M36; WP Leader: LIBER]	35
<i>WP7 Tables 1.2.7.1-7</i>	42

Abbreviations List

SSSA	Sant'Anna School for Advance Studies
UvA-IViR	University of Amsterdam - Institute for Information Law
UGLA-CREATe	University of Glasgow - Creativity, Regulation, Enterprise and Technology Centre
HIIG	Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society
LIBER	Association of European Research Libraries
NUIM	National University of Ireland Maynooth
UTARTU	University of Tartu
UNITN	University of Trento
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
USZ	University of Szeged
WP	Work Package
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
UGC	User-generated content
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
CDSM	Copyright in the Digital Single Market
DSM	Digital Single Market
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
DoA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ABM	Agent-based model
GA	General Assembly
PMB	Project Management Board
PO	Project Officer
EULA	End-user License Agreements
ToS	Terms of Services
EPIP	European Policy for Intellectual Property
inDICES	EU Project "Measuring the impact of Digital Culture"
COMMUNIA	COMMUNIA International Association

List of tables

Table 1.1.1. Objective 1 – Mapping.....	9
Table 1.1.2. Objective 2 – Measuring.....	11
Table 1.1.3. Objective 3 – Engaging.....	13
Table 1.1.4. Objective 4 – Shaping the future.....	14
Table 1.1.5. Milestones M1-M18.....	14
Table 1.2.1. Deliverables M1-M18.....	19
Table 1.2.2. List of Work Packages.....	21
Table 1.2.3. External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) members of <i>reCreating Europe</i>	22
Table 1.2.4. List of GA and PMB meetings of <i>reCreating Europe</i> held in M1-M18.....	22
Table 1.2.7.1 Key Stakeholders in a nutshell.....	42
Table 1.2.7.2 Overall communication collaterals produced in RP1.....	42
Table 1.2.7.3 Summary of dissemination activities in RP1.....	43
Table 1.2.7.4 Status across KPIs as of June 2021.....	44

List of figures

Figure 1.1.1 <i>reCreating Europe</i> roadmap.....	6
Figure 1.2.1. <i>reCreating Europe</i> Gantt chart.....	18
Figure 1.2.7.1 Examples of the <i>reCreating Europe</i> Newsletter.....	38
Figure 1.2.7.2 Virtual banner of the <i>reCreating Europe</i> campaign on World IP Day 2021.....	39
Figure 1.2.7.3. Visual Overview of <i>reCreating Europe</i> 's Social Media Accounts.....	40

1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

This report summarizes the project progress and activities carried out from the beginning of the project *reCreating Europe* (M1 – 1st January 2020) to its Mid Term (M18 – 30th June 2021), providing details on the work performed and effort spent by each partner.

reCreating Europe final goal is to go beyond the state of the art and the approaches adopted up to date, by offering a holistic and multi-disciplinary assessment of the impact of digital copyright on culture and creativity within the context of the digital single market. *reCreating Europe*'s research questions and tasks are articulated around stakeholders and key activities (access, consumption, intermediation, individual and mass creation) in order to provide the first contextual mapping and measurement of key indicators of regulatory efficiency and fairness in each of the policy areas involved in the debate, and with reference to the most representative interest groups. From the access and consumption side, *reCreating Europe* offers a complete cross-national mapping of public and private ordering sources and measures that enable or hinder digital access to culture, with an additional and specific focus on vulnerable groups (people with disabilities, minorities), and it couples it with a measurement of users' knowledge of copyright and perceptions of access problems, and a mapping and assessment of alternative strategies adopted by users and specific communities or networks (e.g. academics and people with visual impairments) to overcome regulatory obstacles to access and sharing. The same approach is adopted with regard to GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) institutions, intermediaries (namely large-scale UGC (User-generated content) platforms), creators and performers, including the emerging role of AI machines as producers of literary or artistic works. The cross-feeding of research methods and results between vertical WPs is further enriched by the constant exchange with stakeholders, which cooperate to the assessment through surveys, interviews and workshops, interacting with open research outputs and participative knowledge creation, and sharing their views on the project's best practices and policy recommendations.

In order to achieve its ground-breaking goal, *reCreating Europe* has organized its activities and grouped its objectives around two domains (knowledge and policy) and four pillars (mapping, measuring, engaging and shaping the future). The **domain of knowledge** aims to break through the state of the art and to provide comprehensive data set on a range of partially unexplored sectors and research questions, which are of key relevance to support a 360° data-driven copyright reform that takes into account all its potential spin off in other policy realms. The **domain of policy** builds on the results of "knowledge" to offer best practices to stakeholders, raise awareness, shape perceptions, and formulate policy recommendations for the EU and national regulators.

Figure 1.1.1 *reCreating Europe* roadmap

The project pillar “**mapping**”, under the knowledge domain, is being implemented by offering detailed overviews of public and private regulatory solutions in specific sectors (*inter alia* end users and access to

culture, authors' remuneration, artificial intelligence and data training models, documentary filmmaking, immersive digital heritage technologies, online platform and content moderation and removal etc.), mapped and assessment not only via desk research but also through participatory research tools, such as sector-specific online workshops and deliberative exercises. This approach has offered the possibility to gather important insight on perceptions, awareness and strategy of key stakeholders *vis-à-vis* the regulatory framework and its bottlenecks.

More specifically, with regard to end users, *reCreating Europe* is collecting and constantly updating data on the legislative, judicial and contractual practice in the field of copyright flexibilities in all Member States, and assessing their impact on access, consumption and use of cultural and creative content. On the side of vulnerable groups, it is assessing the extent to which they experience discrimination and stigma, as well as practical barriers, in accessing culture, and it is investigating whether and to what extent digital policies might enhance or counteract practices that maintain inequality. In the broad area of creative industries, it is conducting an in-depth evaluation of nature, features and impact of copyright territoriality in the Digital Single Market, studying – on the basis of empirical data - entrepreneurship patterns of creative industries in gentrifying urban neighbourhoods, investigating existing literature on and behaviours in sectors characterized by “creativity without IP” (so called “IP negative spaces”), and assessing the perception and impact of copyright exceptions on documentary filmmakers and immersive digital heritage practitioners. In the field of cultural heritage institutions (specifically in the GLAM sector), *reCreating Europe* is analysing governance and implementation of processes for IPRs (Intellectual Property Rights), and sector-specific practices on content digitisation. On the side of intermediaries, it is mapping legal rules and private practices regulating the moderation and removal of copyright-protected content in large-scale UGC platforms.

The project pillar “**measuring**”, complementing mapping in the knowledge domain, is being implemented by assessing, on the basis of empirical data, *inter alia*, access to and fruition of born digital and digitised content, users' perceptions on digitisation and copyright and their impact on consumption patterns, the effectivity of regulatory measures to increase digital access in specific sectors, the experiences, perceptions and income developments of creators and performers, the impact on laws and practices on content moderation and removal on access and dissemination of culture online.

The project pillar “**engaging**”, under the domain of policy, is covering all the objectives including participatory research activities and stakeholders' involvement that, both in the vertical and the horizontal WPs, channel the experiences, needs, awareness level of all the market and non-market actors involved in the debate, for example engaging with creative hubs in a specific location, involving documentary filmmakers and immersive digital heritage practitioners in the discussion on copyright flexibilities, conducting semi-structured interviews with representatives of vulnerable groups, organizing workshop, focus groups and conferences by targeting as speakers and audience key stakeholders (see, e.g. the workshops and conferences held under WP2 on copyright flexibilities, and the general project conference on the implementation of the CDSM (Copyright in the Digital Single Market) Directive).

The project pillar “**shaping the future**” is already transforming all the project's findings into policy recommendations and best practices that suggest the appropriate level of copyright harmonization within the DSM (Digital Single Market), remove the barriers created by the current regulatory framework to access to culture for all, including vulnerable groups, and to the democratic thriving of creative and cultural practices and businesses. For example, WP4 has already generated policy recommendations. Following the suggestion of the *reCreating Europe* team, the UK (United Kingdom) Feature Docs initiative – in their policy report “Making It Real: A Policy Programme for UK Independent Documentary Film” (see: <https://ukfd.org.uk/policy-reports/>) – proposes to ‘Develop a code of practice for fair use’ as part of a new policy programme for the UK documentary film industry. They set up a Screen Heritage Working Group to enact this proposal in collaboration with *reCreating Europe*, Task 4.3.

1.1. Objectives' status M1-M18

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound and disruptive effect on the hiring of new staff, the implementation of participatory research strategies, and the ability of academic staff in universities to perform research, especially as great efforts needed to be concentrated on adjusting programs, methods and schedules to the new remote education settings. Despite this, researchers within *reCreating Europe* have put in exceptional effort and have succeeded in carrying out the work described in the amended Grant Agreement.

Achievements and activities carried out so far are in line with the Workplan described in Annex 1 (Part A) and with the Description of the Actions (DoA - Part B) of the Grant Agreement, as amended in September 10th, 2020 through the Amendment request No AMD-870626-3.

Referring to section 1.1 of the DoA (Annex 1 – Part B), *reCreating Europe* defined the following expected results and measurable indicators for its four objectives. Within the first 18 Months the following activities have been carried out in order to achieve each of them.

Table 1.1.1. Objective 1 – Mapping

Expected specific results	Status of results at M18	Expected Deliverables	Deliverables at M18	Overall expected KPIs	KPIs at M18
Comparative and EU cross-national mapping of regulatory and private ordering sources impacting on access to culture	Results have been achieved and showed in D2.1 entitled <i>Interim report on EU and national sources and private practices on legitimate uses and flexibilities</i> due and submitted in M12.	D2.1	D2.1	1 Internal database ; 1 Report	1 Internal database: The chart of the collected data on private ordering sources is available via https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ObQ63uX6Z8sRAQgU207OzOX96qvXXXQG/view?usp=sharing 1 Report: D2.1 available in Zenodo project repository
Cross-national mapping of legal, economic and tech barriers to access for vulnerable groups	Results have been achieved and showed in D2.2 entitled <i>Interim report on barriers experienced by vulnerable groups</i> due and submitted in M18.	D2.2	D2.2	1 Report	1 public Report available in Zenodo project repository: D2.2
Cross-national mapping of literature and state-of-the-art knowledge on income development of authors and performers in the EU and on copyright reversal	This objective is part of Task 3.1 which started in M7 and lasts until M25. By M18, the work on the survey which will yield D3.2 and D3.2 has been initiated, following up on the work in D3.1 D3.1 entitled <i>Mapping document on income development of authors and performer in the EU and on copyright reversal</i> will be completed timely at the end of M20.	D3.1	None	1 Report	None
Assessment of role of AI machines in producing literary and artistic content, impact on human creators and the protection of literary and	This objective is part of Task 3.2 which started in M3 and lasts until M21. By M18, the work is on schedule. Interim report D3.4 entitled <i>Interim report on the role of AI machines in producing literary and artistic content ("AI Music Outputs: Challenges to the</i>	D3.4; D3.5	D3.4	2 Reports	1 public Report available in Zenodo project repository: D3.4

artistic productions of AI machines under EU copyright	<i>Copyright Legal Framework</i>) was delivered with a slight delay in the course of M16 and final report D3.5 entitled <i>Final report on the impact of IA authorship</i> will be completed timely in M21.				
Cross-national mapping of harmonisation of the reproduction and adaptation right and connected exceptions (“legal cartography”) and of the role of EU copyright law in relation to training models for machine learning purposes.	This objective is part of Task 3.3 which started in M4 and lasts until M28. By M18, the work is on schedule. Interim report D3.6 entitled <i>Interim report on harmonisation of rights of reproduction and adaptation and connected exceptions</i> was delivered on time in M18 and final report D3.7 entitled <i>Final report on the role of EU copyright law in relation to training models for machine learning purposes</i> will be completed timely in M28.	D3.6; D3.7	D3.6	2 Reports	1 public Report available in Zenodo project repository: D3.6
Cross-national, mapping of legal framework regulating digitized and digital-born content for Galleries and Museums (GM) and for Libraries and Archives (LA)	Results have been achieved and showed in D5.1 entitled <i>Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) industries in EU</i> due and submitted in M18 and in D5.2 entitled <i>Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU</i> due and submitted in M12.	D5.1; D5.2		2 Reports	2 public Reports available in Zenodo project repository: D5.1 ; D5.2
Comparative and EU cross-national mapping of regulatory and private ordering sources impacting content moderation and removal	Results have been achieved and showed in: - D6.1 entitled <i>Interim report on mapping of EU legal framework and intermediaries’ practices on copyright content moderation and</i>	D6.1	D6.1	1 Report	1 public Report available in Zenodo project repository: D6.1 1 reported Milestone available in Zenodo project repository: MS1

at scale in online platforms	removal due in M16 and submitted with a slight delay in M18. - Milestone 1 entitled <i>Mapping Legal Framework - Methodology and Design</i> due and achieved in M5.				
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Table 1.1.2. Objective 2 – Measuring

Expected specific results	Status of results at M18	Expected Deliverables	Deliverables at M18	Overall expected KPIs	KPIs at M18
Agent-based model of cultural consumption in different context	The development of these ABM (Agent-based models) encompasses several phases, two of which has been work subject of M1-M18. The starting point was to review the existing literature to identify key actors, empirical relations, and stylised facts characterising the context of the analysis. The second step entailed the development of the model structure with the disposition of the relations between the modelled agents (i.e. the consumers), the institutions (i.e. the way the copyright law is applied and enforced) and the effect of technology (i.e. digitalisation). In this phase, it was also essential to lay down the timeline of the model and the actions that each actor can take at any point in time.	D2.3	None	1 Report on AB results	Preliminary results on the model have been circulated between the SSSA team to collect feedback and work on improvements.
Assessing how digitisation and copyright perception shape consumption (survey)	Since the beginning of the project, the work has been mainly preparatory, focusing on drafting the new survey and the procurement of the survey services. Since the drafting of the project, for data comparability, we wanted to outsource the survey to the same provider that	D2.7	None	1 Report (study) and 1 data set	None

	<p>performed the previous "Global Online Piracy Study" of 2018, and in the budget, 40k are devoted to this purchase. As SSSA is an Italian public University, it is subject to several regulations regarding transparency and procurement that made quite lengthy this direct procurement without a tender. Furthermore, UvA-IViR could secure additional funding for the survey to include more countries than initially proposed in the proposal. While these funds provide the opportunity to enlarge the study scope, the operation needed clearance by the PO, determining some delay.</p> <p>At M18, the survey is ready, and the procurement contract is about to be signed.</p>				
Case studies on effectiveness of regulatory measures to increase digital access (academics; people with visual impairments)	Results have been achieved and showed in D2.5 entitled <i>Interim report on case studies</i> due and submitted in M18.	D2.5	D2.5	2 Reports on case studies and 2 data sets	1 public Report available in Zenodo project repository: D2.5
Data set and final report on experiences and perceptions of authors and performers throughout EU and digitisation and copyright in the DSM.	This objective is part of Task 3.1 which started in M7 and lasts until M25. By M18, the work on the survey which will yield D3.2 entitled <i>A data set perspectives authors and performers</i> due in month 22 and D3.3 entitled <i>Final report perspectives authors and performers</i> due in month 25 had been initiated, following up on the work in D3.1 entitled <i>Mapping document on income development of authors and performer in the EU and on copyright reversal</i> due in M20.	D3.2; D3.3	None	1 Report and 1 data set	None

Assessing how EU law, National law, and platform rules and practices on copyright content moderation and removal impact access to and dissemination of culture online	Work is ongoing in D.6.2 entitled <i>Mapping Report</i> due in M21. Most key developments at the legal and policy level have been taken into account in the legal and empirical research, although delays at the judicial and policy level have caused delays in the research (namely in the Commission Guidance on art. 17 CDSM Directive and on the AG Opinion in C-401/19 - Poland v Parliament and Council).	D6.2	None	1 Report (study)	None
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Table 1.1.3. Objective 3 – Engaging

Expected specific results	Status of results at M18	Expected Deliverables	Deliverables at M18	Overall expected KPIs	KPIs at M18
Engagement and outreach through engagement activities, dissemination materials, website (incl. Stakeholders’ platform) and other communication means	Expected results at M18 have been achieved are showed in: - D7.1 entitled <i>Engagement and Outreach Strategy</i> due and submitted in M18. - D7.2 entitled <i>Project’s brand identity, communication kit and website</i> due and submitted in M2. - Milestone 2 entitled <i>Stakeholder landscape analysis</i> due and submitted in M4. - Milestone 8 entitled <i>Evaluation of engagement strategy</i> due and submitted in M18.	D7.1; D7.2;D7.3	D7.1 D7.2	Reports, Website branding and communications kit	12 public Reports available in Zenodo project repository: D2.1 , D2.2 , D2.5 , D3.4 , D4.2 , D4.6 , D4.8 , D4.10 , D4.12 , D5.1 , D5.2 , D6.1 . 1 Website: https://www.recreating.eu/ 1 branding and communications kit: D7.2 2 reported Milestones available in Annex 1 and Annex 2 to this document: MS2; MS8
Building expertise, providing training to stakeholders and urging them to share their own material	Expected results at M18 have been achieved are showed in: Milestone 4 entitled <i>Expertise building framework</i> due and submitted in M18.	D7.4	None	Training toolkit and building expertise framework	1 reported Milestone available in Annex 3 to this document: MS4

Table 1.1.4. Objective 4 – Shaping the future

Expected specific results	Status of results at M18	Expected Deliverables	Deliverables at M18	Overall expected KPIs	KPIs at M18
Best practices for targeted stakeholders and policy recommendations	Work ongoing; no results to be reported so far.	D2.6; D4.7 D5.7; D6.2	None	6 best practices and 4 policy recommendations (and related reports)	None
Guidelines & FAQs helping GLAMS dealing with laws regulating digital content	Expected results at M18 regard the achievements showed in D5.4 entitled <i>Guidelines & FAQs (LA) industries – Interim version.</i>	D5.3; D5.4, D5.5, D5.6	D5.4	4 Sets of Guidelines and of FAQs	1 public Report available in Zenodo project repository: D5.4
Copyright User portal	Expected results at M18 regard the achievements showed in D4.12 entitled <i>Interim report on the information architecture of the Copyright User EU site.</i>	D4.12; D4.13 (website)	D4.12	Website	D4.12 public Report available in Zenodo project repository provides information on the architecture of the website CopyrightUser.eu under definition.

Table 1.1.5. Milestones M1-M18

Milest. No.	Milestone title	Related WP(s) No.	Lead beneficiary	Delivery date (Annex 1)	Delivery date (actual)	Achieved	Means of verification
MS1	Mapping Legal Framework - Methodology and Design	WP6	UvA-IViR	31/05/2020	31/05/2020	YES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Webinar report (<i>ReCreating Europe</i> Website): https://www.recreating.eu/public-and-regulatory-framework-of-online-intermediaries-workshop/ - Additional Report (Copy21 website): http://copy21.com/2020/05/public-and-regulatory-framework-of-online-intermediaries-conference-report/ - Online recording (YouTube): https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n9RccSMBSjE&t=5s

							<p>- Presentation Slides (Zenodo): https://zenodo.org/record/3833714#Xs4188ZS9QK - Twitter: see @reCreatingEU (5.05.2020) <i>More details are provided in the MS1 report available in Zenodo project repository.</i></p>
MS2	Stakeholder landscape analysis	WP7	LIBER	30/04/2020	30/04/2020	YES	<p>Stakeholder Landscape Analysis report: it provides an overview of the stakeholder mapping exercise carried out recently, where all project partners provided input on potential stakeholders (individual organizations) that they think have a close link to the project and should potentially be engaged in future project activities.</p> <p>Stakeholder Mapping Database: it looks at specific organizations, identifies to which stakeholder category they belong to and the level of their interest in and potential influence on the project. It also indicates the project partner that already has some kind of communication established with the organization to leverage on and enhance these connections when reaching out to the stakeholders. During this stakeholder mapping exercise more than 100 individual organizations have been identified so far and the database will be kept “open” for further inclusion during the project. WP7 asks project partners will update this database on a regular basis and include additional stakeholders identified later in the project. <i>More details are provided in Annex 1 (MS2 report) to this document.</i></p>
MS3	Four deliberative exercises to identify acceptable normative practices within a progressive interpretation of the legal framework	WP4	UGLA-CREAtE	30/06/2021	30/06/2021	YES	<p>The four workshops were initially intended to be real-live events, to be held in the Netherlands and the UK respectively, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, we had to organize them as online workshops. The online workshops were held at the following dates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UK workshop documentary filmmakers: Monday 22 March 2021 - NL workshop documentary filmmakers: Monday 29 March 2021 - UK workshop immersive cultural heritage: Monday 10 May 2021 - NL workshop immersive cultural heritage: Monday 17 May 2021. <p>Video recordings have been made of the four workshops, which are on file with the authors. To get maximum input for the issue reports and increase openness of discussion, it was agreed with the participants upfront that the workshops were held under the Chatham House Rule, according to which all participants are free to use information from the</p>

							discussion, but not to reveal who made any comment. It was also agreed with the participants that the video recordings of the workshops would not be disseminated. <i>More details are provided in the MS3 report available in Zenodo project repository.</i>
MS4	Expertise building framework	WP7	LIBER	31/12/2020	07/12/2020	YES	A <i>ReCreating Europe</i> Training Toolkit is planned to catalogue the training materials produced by the project, with the aspiration to be used at a later stage as a place where key stakeholders will catalogue their training materials as well. The Toolkit will be embedded on the ReCreating Europe website and will operate under the FAIR principles. The Toolkit was initially imagined as an element of the Stakeholders' platform. As the website progressed overall in a Stakeholder-focused way of presenting activities and materials, the Toolkit will have a dedicated space under the project's resources. A link to the portal for information on the EU copyright law, the dedicated site CopyrightUser.eu under development (D4.12), will be added to the Toolkit at the end of the project. <i>More details are provided in Annex 3 (MS4 report) to this document.</i>
MS5	Issue reports of how copyright exceptions and other permitted uses are understood and applied by documentary film makers and immersive digital heritage practitioners in the Netherlands and the UK	WP4	UGLA-CRETe	30/06/2021	30/06/2021	YES	As explained also in respect of MS3, transcripts and/or written accounts were made of the online workshops held at the following dates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UK workshop documentary filmmakers: Monday 22 March 2021 - NL workshop documentary filmmakers: Monday 29 March 2021 - UK workshop immersive cultural heritage: Monday 10 May 2021 - NL workshop immersive cultural heritage: Monday 17 May 2021 The transcripts and written accounts of the four workshops are on file with the authors. To get maximum input for the issue reports and increase openness of discussion, it was agreed with the participants upfront that the workshops were held under the Chatham House Rule, according to which all participants are free to use information from the discussion, but not to reveal who made any comment. It was also agreed with the participants that the transcripts and accounts would not be disseminated, as they could perhaps be traceable to participants of the workshop. The four issue reports written on the basis of the transcriptions and accounts have been directly and fully integrated in D4.10 .

							<i>More details are provided in the MS5 report available in Zenodo project repository.</i>
MS8	Evaluation of engagement strategy	WP7	LIBER	30/06/2021	30/06/2021	YES	<p>The verification means of this Milestone is the evaluation of the engagement strategy itself. The steps used for the evaluation of the strategy are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sharing updates and verifying the engagement and outreach activities with the <i>reCreating Europe</i> project partners at the level of a) WP7 Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach in monthly meetings, b) Project Management board meetings (both regular and extraordinary), c) General Assembly meetings (both regular and extraordinary). - Regularly collecting information and updates related to engagement and building expertise activities and checking across the set KPIs for outreach and impact. - Taking into consideration the COVID-19 pandemic repercussions had on the project overall and adjustments that needed to be made. - Taking into consideration the information as per the Amendment No AMD-870626-3 regarding the timeline of deliverables and its impact on engagement and building expertise activities. - As the project also aims to engage through building expertise, the current milestone is taking into consideration the MS4 Building Expertise Framework. - <i>ReCreating Europe</i> partners providing input for the current Milestone as per the engagement and outreach activities targeting each key stakeholder group. - Regular updates are provided by WP coordinators. <p><i>More details are provided in Annex 2 (MS8 report) to this document.</i></p>

1.2 Explanation of the work carried per WP in M1-M18

reCreating Europe is being implemented through 5 vertical, stakeholder-based work packages (WPs) (WP2 to WP6) and 2 horizontal WPs, WP1 covering management and coordination activities and WP7 which is fed by the technical and scientific inputs of WP2-WP6 and is maximizing the impact of the project through proactive engagement and dissemination. The following project Gantt chart has been amended on September 10th, 2020.

Referring to section 1.3 of the amended Workplan (Annex 1- Part A), *reCreating Europe* has released and submitted to the EC all deliverables expected in the reporting period M1-M18.

Table 1.2.1. Deliverables M1-M18

No	WP No	Del Rel. No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Dissemination Level	Est. Del. Date (Annex I)	Actual Del. Date	Status
1	WP1	D1.1	Data management plan	SSSA	Public	31 Mar 2020	31 Mar 2020	Submitted
2	WP1	D1.2	Informed consent forms and information sheets	SSSA	Confidential	31 Mar 2020	31 Mar 2020	Submitted
3	WP2	D2.1	Interim report on EU and national sources and private practices on legitimate uses and flexibilities	SSSA	Public	31 Dec 2020	29 Dec 2020	Submitted
4	WP2	D2.2	Interim report on barriers experienced by vulnerable groups	NUIM	Public	30 Jun 2021	27 Jun 2021	Submitted
5	WP2	D2.5	Interim report on case studies	NUIM	Public	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	Submitted
6	WP3	D3.4	Interim report on the role of AI machines in producing literary and artistic content	UvA-IViR	Public	31 Mar 2021	23 Apr 2021	Submitted
7	WP3	D3.6	Interim report on harmonisation of rights of reproduction and adaptation and connected exceptions.	UGLA-CREAtE	Public	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	Submitted
8	WP4	D4.1	Territoriality scoping paper	UvA-IViR	Public	31 Dec 2020	12 Apr 2021	Submitted
9	WP4	D4.2	Report on EU policy space in light of international framework	UvA-IViR	Public	30 Jun 2021	30 Jun 2021	Submitted
10	WP4	D4.6	Interim report on negative space of EU creative industries	SSSA	Public	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	Submitted
11	WP4	D4.8	Interim report on entrepreneurship patterns of creative industries in gentrifying urban neighbourhoods arising from empirical data gathered	UTARTU	Public	30 Jun 2021	30 Jun 2021	Submitted
12	WP4	D4.10	Issue reports on how copyright exceptions and other permitted uses that are relevant for documentary filmmakers and immersive digital heritage practitioners are understood in the Netherlands and the UK	UGLA-CREAtE	Public	30 Jun 2021	30 Jun 2021	Submitted

13	WP4	D4.12	Interim report on the information architecture of the Copyright User EU site	UGLA-CREAtE	Public	30 Jun 2021	30 Jun 2021	Submitted
14	WP5	D5.1	Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) industries in EU	UNITN	Public	30 Jun 2021	30 Jun 2021	Submitted
15	WP5	D5.2	Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU	SSSA	Public	31 Dec 2020	30 Dec 2020	Submitted
16	WP5	D5.4	Guidelines & FAQs (LA) industries – Interim version	LIBER	Public	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	Submitted
17	WP6	D6.1	Interim report on mapping of EU legal framework and intermediaries' practices on copyright content moderation and removal	UvA-IViR	Public	30 Apr 2021	01 Jun 2021	Submitted
18	WP7	D7.1	Engagement and Outreach Strategy	LIBER	Confidential	30 Jun 2020	01 Jul 2020	Submitted
19	WP7	D7.2	Project's brand identity, communication kit and website	SSSA	Public	29 Feb 2020	01 Mar 2020	Submitted

The following is the amended timeline of *reCreating Europe* work packages. With respect to the original duration, the amendment has affected WP3 extended from M24 to M28 and some Tasks (T2.2 extended from M30 to M36, T3.1 extended from M24 to M25, T3.2 extended from M20 to M21, T3.3 extended from M20 to M28, T6.2 extended from M18 to M21) which detailed status will be provided in the following sections.

Table 1.2.2. List of Work Packages

WP No	WP Title	Lead beneficiary	Start month	End month
WP1	Management and coordination	1 - SSSA	1	36
WP2	End users and access to culture	1 - SSSA	1	36
WP3	Authors and performers	2 - UvA-IViR	3	28
WP4	Creative industries	3 - UGLA-CREAtE	1	36
WP5	Galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM)	8 - UNITN	1	36
WP6	Intermediaries (Copyright Content Moderation and Removal at Scale in the Digital Single Market: What Impact on Access to Culture?)	2 - UvA-IViR	1	33
WP7	Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach	5 - LIBER	1	36

Activities carried out in this reporting period are in line with the amended timeline.

1.2.1 Work Package 1 – Management and Coordination [M1-M36; WP Leader: SSSA]

WP1 and its Tasks last from month 1 to month 36 of the project. The work is coordinated by SSSA and is successfully implemented as a result of an active involvement all project beneficiaries.

All WP1 tasks and objectives planned for M1-M18 have been accomplished and all deliverables of the period have been submitted. Status and deviations of the objectives have been regularly assessed in the periodic General Assembly (GA) and Project Management Board (PMB) meetings. There are no major deviations in terms of use of resources in this reporting period.

T1.1 - Project coordination has in this reporting period: successfully launched and developed the project, including by setting up project governance bodies and the external advisory board (Table 1.2.3 below) and by developing project management and quality assurance plan (M4), procedures and tools; monitored the progress of the deliverables prepared and released in this reporting period; prepared and released the data management plan; ensured the efficient communication within the consortium and with the EC Project Officer (PO); set up shared IT tools for cooperation, communication and documents' sharing such as Dropbox and Teams; successfully guided and put in place the internal and external risk management processes, including during the COVID-19 pandemic situation especially in M3-M9 and beyond of the project; successfully guided the project amendment process, due to the pandemic-related difficulties, concluded with the approved amendment by the EC on M9; guaranteed a smooth everyday management of the consortium; organised and coordinated several ordinary and extraordinary GA and PMB meetings.

Table 1.2.3. External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) members of reCreating Europe

No	Name and Surname	Role
1	Alexander Peukert	Professor of Civil Law and Commercial Law, Goethe University Frankfurt
2	Jane C. Ginsburg	Morton L. Janklow Professor of Literary & Artistic Property Law, Columbia Law School
3	David Keane	Assistant Professor, Dublin City University
4	Peter Jaszi	Professor of Law Emeritus, American University School of Law
5	Anna Lawson	Professor of Law, University of Leeds
6	Lionel Bently	Herchel Smith Professor of Intellectual Property, University of Cambridge
7	Bruno de Witte	Professor of European Law, Maastricht University; part-time Professor of Law, European University Institute
8	Severine Dusollier	Professor of Law, Sciences Po Law School
9	Indrek Ibrus	Professor of Media Innovation, Baltic Film, Media, Arts, and Communication School, Tallinn University
10	Ruth Towse	Professor of Economics of Creative Industries, Bournemouth University
11	Paul Heald	Albert J. Harno and Edward W. Cleary Chair in Law, Illinois College of Law

T1.2 - Scientific management has so far: gave the initial research directions and controlled that the project is in line with its mid-term and final goals and its outcomes are timely released; monitored the work plan and the project progress, including by timely identifying and solving problems; planned and organised the project progress meetings (Table 1.2.4); monitored each partner’s work and results by means of GA meetings or through one-to-one communications; monitored and guaranteed fulfilment and quality assurance of project deliverables and milestones, including by guiding and controlling their quality through the internal peer-review process established within the QA plan.

Table 1.2.4. List of GA and PMB meetings of reCreating Europe held in M1-M18

No	Name of the meeting	Dates and venue/virtual room meeting
1	1st GA	21.01.2020, Pisa (Italy)
2	1st PMB	21.01.2020, Pisa (Italy)
3	2nd PMB	15.04.2020, WebEx
4	1st EX PMB	11.05.2020, WebEx
5	2nd GA	17.07.2020, WebEx
6	3rd PMB	21.09.2020, WebEx
7	12nd EX PMB	26.11.2020, WebEx
8	1st EX GA	15.12.2020, WebEx
9	3rd GA	23.02.2021, WebEx
10	4th PMB	23.02.2021, WebEx
11	5th PMB	26.04.2021, WebEx
12	4th GA	15.06.2021, WebEx
13	3rd EX PMB	15.06.2021, WebEx

T1.3 - Administrative management has so far: monitored and distributed the pre-financing payment of the EC to the partners; regularly monitored the effort spent by each partner in the period; gave advice on the financial statements to be delivered with this periodic report.

T1.4 - Data protection, data management plan and ethics compliance has so far: developed and released on M3 the *Data management plan (D1.1)*, documenting the types of data the project will generate or collect, the standards and platforms that will be used for storage and processing, measures to assure legal compliance and the plan for how these data will be curated and preserved to enable maximal future

exploitation, sharing and re-use. Along with D1.1, T1.4 has developed and released on M3 *Informed consent forms and information sheets (D1.2)* to be used by partners when conducting participatory research activities.

1.2.2 Work Package 2 – End users and access to culture [M1-M36; WP Leader: SSSA]

SSSA coordinates WP2 work whose tasks last from month 1 to month 36 of the project. Planned tasks and objectives have been accomplished, and deliverables due by M18 have been submitted on time. There are no significant deviations in terms of the use of resources in this reporting period.

WP2 directly contributes to three pillars of the project, focussing on end-users and access to culture with an interdisciplinary outlook, conjugating both law and economics research. WP2 leverages upon such differences to identify and address the legal, economic and technological challenges faced by selected vulnerable users (people with disabilities, minorities) in accessing digital culture and evaluate the adequacy of existing EU and national regulatory responses to tackle such problems.

Task 2.1 Comparative and EU cross-national mapping of regulatory and private ordering sources [M1-M30; Lead partner: SSSA. Contributors: NUIM, USZ], aims to provide a cross-national mapping with an assessment of legal and policy measures impacting on access to culture for both general users and selected vulnerable groups looking at two specific layers. SSSA is responsible for Subtask 2.2.1 mapping regulatory sources, court decisions, governmental policies, practices, and schemes in copyright law, DSM, and broader cultural policies. At the same time, USZ is responsible for Subtask 2.2.2, mapping the private ordering mechanisms of selected online platforms related to end-user flexibilities and compare these platforms End-user License Agreements (EULA) or Terms of Services (ToS) to assess their flexibility.

The SSSA team investigated public legal sources, focusing on legislative provisions, governmental policies, and court decisions in the field of copyright law and cultural policies. After an in-depth study of the state of the art on copyright flexibilities, a wide-ranging cross-national legal mapping has been structured and conducted thanks to the involvement of national legal experts from all 27 Member States. The national experts answering the survey to collect relevant data were selected among the consortium and its broader professional networks. The collection and analysis of public legal sources have led to the submission of an interim report at M12. The comparative analysis and the creation of the public database (to be launched by M30) of the public legal sources are currently ongoing. Synergies have been created with the existing databases (i) [CREATE CDSM Implementation Tracker](#) (this resource was produced as part of the Stakeholder Platform/WP7) and (ii) <https://copyrightexceptions.eu> to join efforts in updating the legal mapping with CDSM-relevant data. An academic article entitled "Betwixt EU and national: the present and future of copyright flexibilities" is currently being drafted and accepted for presentation at the 2021 EPIP (European Policy for Intellectual Property) conference in early September 2021.

USZ preliminary work started with the selection of 17 different online platforms in the field of i) streaming with hosting services (e.g. YouTube, Twitch, and Pornhub), ii) streaming without hosting services (e.g. Spotify, Netflix, and Disney+), iii) online marketplaces (e.g. Amazon, Apple Media Service, and Google Play), and iv) social media platforms (e.g. Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook). USZ mapping exercise firstly consisted of identifying 8 variables related to users' flexibilities (e.g., the extent of the access rights provided to the users, restricted uses, allowance of UGC, technological restrictions on access, or procedural safeguards) to organise and possibly compare these platforms' public ordering mechanisms. In the second phase, excerpts of the EULAs and ToSs were arranged in an extensive Excel chart to facilitate their arrangement in comparable groups.

The article "End-User Flexibilities in Digital Copyright Law – An Empirical Analysis of End-User License Agreements" reports the results on the evaluation and comparison of the collected data. This article will be published in the forthcoming issue of *Interactive Entertainment Law Review*. The manuscript is available in open access at:

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3879740.

Task 2.2 *Assessing legal, economic and technological barriers to access for vulnerable groups* [M1-M36; Lead partner: NUIM. Contributors: SSSA], aims to assess the extent to which vulnerable groups experience barriers in accessing digital cultural content. It also aims to investigate whether and to what extent the EU regulatory framework might exacerbate or counteract those barriers. Given the scope of the analysis, NUIM adopts a socio-legal perspective, boosted by the use of an interdisciplinary methodology. Desk-based research is supported by qualitative methods such as semi-structured interviews and a qualitative survey; both conducted across 12 EU Member States: Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Malta and Spain. Task 2.2 required a long phase of preparation for the interviews and survey, followed by an ongoing phase of data collection and processing and analysis of data, conducted in conjunction with systematic legal analysis.

NUIM has started the preparatory work engaging in desk research and the qualitative and participatory research programming. The COVID-19 pandemic emergency has provided both an opportunity and a challenge for the Task 2.2 work. The forced online transition of most cultural events during the COVID-19 emergency might exacerbate the digital divide and polarisation risk of cutting off people living in rural areas, with fewer opportunities, non-digital natives, and all other categories having difficulty accessing digital content. Because of the timing of the Task 2.2. NUIM could gather timely data on this issue.

However, the pandemic and the uncertainty linked to its duration also represented a significant challenge for the practicalities of the research work and required several adjustments to the phase of data collection. As of M18 of the project, NUIM has completed a significant number of qualitative interviews (with some additional interviews to be completed by the end of July 2021). The team has also completed a qualitative survey, has consolidated the methods for analysing this data, and has initiated the coding and data analysis phase.

The interim report D2.2 delivered on time at M18 includes the preliminary results of this task.

Task 2.3 *Agent-based model of cultural consumption vis-a-vis digitisation and change in IPRs regulation* [M1-M18; Lead partner: SSSA. Contributors: USZ], aims to develop a simulation model to analyse how digitisation and copyright law affect patterns of cultural goods consumption. ABM models provide a bottom-up approach to unfold the emergence of complex relations in different scenarios. The development of these ABM models encompasses several phases. The starting point was to review the existing literature to identify key actors, empirical relations, and stylised facts characterising the analysis context. The second step entailed the development of the model structure with the disposition of the relations between the modelled agents (i.e. the consumers), the institutions (i.e. the way the copyright law is applied and enforced) and the effect of technology (i.e. digitalisation). In this phase, it was also essential to lay down the timeline of the model and the actions that each actor can take at any point in time.

In the context of Task 2.6, a third step which includes the writing of the code is foreseen. It will include the calibration of the model using data collected in the first phase and then the simulation will run. Finally, the results will be validated using statistical technique.

Since the beginning of the project, SSSA teams has been working on the task and are now approaching phase three. Preliminary results on the model have been circulated between the SSSA team to collect feedback and work on improvements. Final results will be included in D2.6 due on M24, in the framework of Task 2.6 activities.

Task 2.4 *The complex relation between digitalisation and copyright law on cultural goods consumption: a survey-based assessment* [M1-M24; Lead partner: SSSA. Contributors: UvA-IViR, USZ] entails updating the "Global Online Piracy Study" performed by UvA in 2018. This study presents a very detailed cross-country and cross-industry picture of channels of consumption of cultural goods. The survey design will highlight the degree of awareness of copyright law in different countries and the level of self-indulgence in copyright violations. The central part of this task is elaborating and procuring the original data collected through a

survey administered in seven representative European countries (France, Germany, The Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Ireland). Initially, the survey should have been done in September 2020, covering the previous year. However, the COVID-19 pandemics completely changed the patterns and channels of consumption of cultural goods such as movies, series and therefore, the SSSA team had to devise a new plan.

Following the approval for extension of D.2.7 release, the SSSA team decided to revise the survey, adding questions to unfold the relation between income and consumption choices. The lockdown period can be exploited to elicit better the effect of income on selecting channels of consumption. The lockdown is a significant shock on the income (i.e. self-employed or workers in specific industries such as tourism) that might change the balance between legal and illegal consumption channels.

Since the beginning of the project, the work has been mainly preparatory, focusing on drafting the new survey and the procurement of the survey services. Since the drafting of the project, for data comparability, we wanted to outsource the survey to the same provider that performed the previous "Global Online Piracy Study", and in the budget, 40.000 euro are devoted to this purchase. As SSSA is an Italian public university, it is subject to several regulations regarding transparency and procurement that made quite lengthy this direct procurement without a tender. Furthermore, UvA could secure additional funding for the survey to include more countries than initially proposed in the proposal. While these funds provide the opportunity to enlarge the study scope, the operation needed clearance by the PO, determining some delay.

At M18, the survey is ready, and the procurement contract is about to be signed. The empirical analysis of the survey will be included in D2.7 due in M24.

NUIM and SSSA are jointly contributing to **Task 2.5 Empirical case studies on the effectiveness of regulatory measures to increase digital access to academics and people with visual impairments [M1-M30; Lead partner: NUIM. Contributors: SSSA, USZ, UNITN]** which examines two empirical case studies assessing the impact of regulatory responses to paradigmatic access issues. In particular, SSSA works on subtask 2.5.1 "*Case study on academics and the research exception*", whereas NUIM works subtask 2.5.2 "*Case study visually impaired people and the so-called Marrakesh VIP exception*". Both case studies are based on survey data administered in six European countries (Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, The Netherlands, and Sweden). While part of the research has been independently carried out, the two units developed an extensive coordination and communication design to ensure comparability of the data gathered.

Working at subtask 2.5.1, the SSSA team is collecting survey-based evidence on the knowledge and perception that academics have on copyright law and their use of Shadow Library websites such as Sci-Hub. Despite digitalisation and existing research and teaching exception to copyright law, access to the scientific literature for academics remains highly costly. Those barriers might profoundly affect the amount of scientific knowledge available in university institutions, also within the EU. An example of the impact of those barriers was the clash between a major publisher and consortia of European universities. The event re-opened the debate on the role of publishers in assessing research quality and on the perceived unfairness of publishers' business models. Starting from these premises, the SSSA survey targeted the population of academics working in top universities to collect data on copyright knowledge, perception and use of digital piracy while carrying out teaching and academic research.

Since M10, a post-doc joined the SSSA team to work on this subtask. Preliminary desk-based research narrowed the scope of the analysis and helped to identify specific research questions. Following this step, the SSSA team prepared the survey and completed the research protocol to be submitted to the SSSA ethical committee. After obtaining the ethical approval on 11 February 2021, the SSSA team started the pilot project by sending the survey to 60 pre-alerted colleagues in different disciplines. While waiting for the ethical approval, finalising the preparatory steps, and preparing the translations, the SSSA team collected more than 130'000 email addresses of scholars working at the top universities in the 6 European countries. We launched the survey on 15 July 2021, and we plan to complete the data collection by M22. An academic article entitled

"Sci-Hub and Academics: survey evidence from EU countries" is currently being drafted and was accepted for presentation at the 2021 EPIP conference, taking place in early September 2021.

NUIM team is conducting the research on Task 2.5.2 to collect survey-based evidence on the knowledge and perception that persons with visual impairments have on copyright law and exceptions and the channels used and barriers faced in accessing printed and digital material.

Similarly to academics, exceptions to copyright law are also implemented for people with visual impairments. In particular, the Marrakesh VIP Treaty (implemented by Directive 2017/1564 and Regulation 2017/1563) is a new mandatory exception to facilitate the creation and dissemination of digital works in an accessible format. As for academics, new technologies might play an essential role in ensuring that visually impaired people access education, entertainment, and other relevant activities in society. However, copyright protection might impede the circulation of accessible copies. Thus the new legal framework might enable the creation and distribution of accessible (non-for-profit) copies of previously inaccessible (copyright-protected) materials. Starting from these premises, NUIM developed a survey for the population of visually impaired people in six selected European countries, recruiting participants through University Disability Offices, self-help groups, self-help activities, and organisations of and for persons with disabilities.

Since the beginning of the project, the NUIM team conducted a preliminary desk-based research reviewing the law literature and the literature related to people with disabilities. Following the relevant literature, the NUIM team identified a set of research questions to address through the survey. NUIM also identified the group of intermediaries through which distribute the survey. The group includes 11 European Blind Union (EBU), Universities Access Offices, and organisations representing blind or visually impaired people. Finally, the ethical committee of the NUIM University just approved the survey, and therefore the translation of the survey and the pilot are about to start.

A complete description of the works undertaken by SSSA and NUIM has been included in the interim report D.2.5 delivered in M18. The empirical results of both tasks are expected in M36.

1.2.3 Work Package 3 – Authors and performers [M1-M28; WP Leader: UvA-IViR]

This WP consists of three tasks that study different issues concerning authors and performers.

Task 3.1 *Perspectives of Creators and performing Artists on Digitization, Copyright and the Digital Single market* [M7-M25; Lead partner: UvA-IViR]

The task is led by UvA-IViR, with a contribution from UGLA-CRETe and a survey targeting a wide range of creators and performers across the EU is its core deliverable (D3.2 and D3.3). The survey questions build in the work in several of the other tasks in the project and on a mapping document of relevant literature and state-of-the-art knowledge (D3.1, due in M20), focussing mainly on the income development of authors and performers and copyright reversal.

A postdoc was hired to work at UvA on deliverable D3.1 (and subsequently D3.2 and D3.3) with 8 months delay due to COVID restrictions, but D3.1 is well under way by M18 and will be completed in time. The work on the survey questionnaire for D3.2 and D3.3 has also been initiated by M18.

Task 3.2 *Growing Role of AI machines as Producers of Literary and Artistic Works: Challenges to Human Authorship* [M3-M21; Lead partner: UvA-IViR]

As described in the Interim Report (D.3.4), considering the evolution of policy in scholarship in this field, UvA has adjusted the focus of the task to better reflect these developments and provide an original contribution to this emerging debate. In particular, the focus of the research is on AI music Outputs and the challenges they pose to the EU copyright legal framework.

There remains significant legal uncertainty about the application of EU copyright and related rights law to outputs generated by or with the assistance of AI systems, tools or techniques (AI outputs). In light of this uncertainty, Task 3.2 examines the following (descriptive and normative) research question: how can and should EU copyright and related rights law protect AI musical outputs? The main aims of this research are three-fold: (i) to analyse the protection of AI outputs under EU copyright and related rights law; (ii) to examine the attribution of authorship and ownership to (natural and legal) persons involved in the creation or production of AI outputs; (iii) to formulate interpretative guidelines and policy recommendations on increasing legal certainty regarding the protection, authorship, and ownership of copyright and/related rights over AI outputs, especially music outputs.

The methodology of this task consists of doctrinal legal research and empirical research through interviews. The doctrinal legal research includes extensive literature review and analysis of primary sources, legal scholarship, empirical literature on AI relevant for our research, literature and published interviews with artists, engineers, and managers of AI projects in the music sector. We have carried out the majority of this work in connection with D.3.4 and until M18. In addition, we carry out empirical research in the form of interviews with experts on the legal, technological and business aspects of AI music outputs. The data and insights from these interviews are included in our analysis, in particular to validate our findings, and develop case studies to support our research. This will be reflected in our Final Report (D.3.5).

A postdoc was hired to work at UvA on Task 3.2. The Interim Report (D.3.4) was concluded and accepted. At time of writing, most of the planned interviews with experts have been carried out or scheduled and will be concluded by M20 (n=10); the Final Report (D3.5) is being prepared to be delivered by M21.

Task 3.3 AI, Machine learning and EU copyright law: ownership issues in training data [M3-M21; Lead partner: UGLA-CREATe]

The task focuses on Machine Learning (ML) as a key technology for the creation and dissemination of knowledge. In particular, the task looks at “input data” i.e., at the information that ML algorithms need to create new knowledge, or in other words to “learn”.

The scope of this task (as detailed in the *interim report*) is to assess how proprietary or quasi-proprietary assertions on information and data (e.g. right of reproduction), or vice versa limits to such attempts (e.g. copyright exceptions), will shape the future of this technology. As ML is becoming central to creative and cultural productions, its regulation will necessarily influence creativity and culture and the values they convey. To achieve the goals of this project, it is therefore essential to understand the interface between technology and the law, to identify critical regulatory gaps, and to propose evidence-informed solutions.

The research design we adopted for this task is a reverse inductive strategy. We focus on case studies of three technological processes to explore in detail possible descriptions that would allow legal analysis, and an assessment of the need for a harmonisation of rights and connected exceptions under copyright law. The case studies were selected in consultation with stakeholders, reflecting a need by scientific researchers and technology companies for a better legal understanding of what they do. They are designed to reflect a range of techniques and processes that underpin advanced data analytics, responding to the EU policy objective of supporting innovation in this field (see interim report for details; a resource page was prepared to document this task and is available at: <https://www.create.ac.uk/legal-approaches-to-data-scraping-mining-and-learning/>).

In parallel, the task produced a thorough analysis of the policy rationale and legal context for the introduction of the two exceptions for text and data mining in the CDSM Directive (Arts 3 and 4 CDSM) which includes an analysis of how the right of reproduction (Art. 2 ISD) and its limitations (mainly Art. 5(1) ISD) interface with the overall regulatory framework of data analytics. This was written as a self-contained scientific paper. In the final report, we will consolidate the conclusions reached in the interim (accounting for technological

advancements) and we will complete the legal analysis around the right of adaptation which, given the characteristics of its harmonization, will be investigated separately, employing a dedicated methodology.

A post-doc was hired at UGLA-CREATe. The interim report (D.3.6) was prepared and submitted on time.

1.2.4 Work Package 4 – Creative industries [M1-M36; WP Leader: UGLA-CREATe]

Task 4.1 *Territorial rights in the DSM* [M1-M36; Lead partner: UvA-IViR]

Task 4.1 involves the production of three deliverables in the shape of papers/reports and two workshops/focus groups over the course of the 3-year project. Three research staff at UvA have performed the necessary research (desk research of regulation, case law, policy documents, academic literature, etc.) for both the Scoping paper on territoriality in the Digital Single Market (D4.1) and the Report on EU policy space in light of international framework (D4.2). Due to COVID-19 effects D4.1 experienced some delay, while D4.2 was delivered in M18 as scheduled.

Task 4.2 *New business models in the European creative industries* [M1-M36; Lead partner: SSSA. Contributor: UTARTU]

Two teams were working during the reporting period on three sub-tasks within these tasks and the work on the sub-tasks is described below.

Regarding **sub-task 4.2.1**, carried out by UTARTU, the initial structure of the report and plan of activities has been established. Based on the structure and the main concept of the report, the team has drafted two original research papers. A paper entitled “Asymmetries of multi-sided platforms: once an idea is shared, it is lost for the owner?” is ready to be submitted to an academic journal, IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management (impact factor 6.146). The paper is based on 19 interviews with users of the largest free 3D model sharing platform GrabCAD. It focuses on the controversies around intellectual property rights over 3D artwork, original creation that has the potential to materialize when fed into 3D printers.

The second paper was close to completion at the end of the reporting period and another leading journal, Research Policy (impact factor 8.11), was identified as an appropriate place of publication as a reaction to the special issue call titled “Are intellectual property rights working for society?”. To be submitted by the Estonian team (UTARTU), the paper furthers the discussion of the controversies of the previous paper on free 3D printing design sharing platforms and IPR. It combines the insights from the above-mentioned qualitative interviews, but also document analysis and user profile analysis. Free content sharing platforms are challenging the boundaries of IPRs as platform business reveals the presence of both too rigid and ineffective IPR systems. The team investigates how the protection of the IPRs of maker community members depends on the platform lifecycle. As the preliminary results show, the ineffectiveness of IPR protection grows in parallel with the degree of heterogeneity among user groups. The core problem behind ineffective IPR protection is the asymmetrical administration of user metadata by the platforms. In the end, the study offers a theoretical contribution by developing an IPR lifecycle theory.

With sub-task 4.2.2., SSSA is in charge of setting the groundwork for the identification and research design of case studies of so-called ‘negative intellectual property spaces’. This literature investigates how some economic sectors manage to be creative and/or innovative despite the lack of intellectual property (IP) protection. Some industries thrive without IP law, either because formal IP does not apply to their innovative activities, or because they choose not to resort to IP law. The study of negative IP spaces can be highly instructive on the interplay between innovation and the incentives set by IP law. Task 4.2.2. kicked off later than expected, as the appointment of the researcher in charge of the Task was delayed because of complications related to the COVID-19 pandemic. Nevertheless, the Interim report on negative space of EU creative industries (D.4.6.) was submitted on time. This report constitutes a fundamental theoretical premise for future developments, as it provides, through extensive desk research by the Sant’Anna team, a systematic literature review and a new taxonomy of the studies of negative IP spaces developed so far (as outlined in

the interim report D.4.6.). This theoretical work will be a fundamental premise for the design of the case studies which will be developed in M18-36 under subtask 4.6.2., leading to D.4.7.

Regarding **sub-task 4.2.3** carried out by UTARTU, the first 18 months have resulted in the D4.8 interim report on entrepreneurship patterns of creative industries in gentrifying urban neighbourhoods arising from empirical data gathered. The plan of activities and applicable methodology was established based on desk research, literature search and internal brainstorming within the UTARTU team and WP4 leaders. The data was collected by means of a series of case studies on micro and small-sized enterprises situated in the creative hubs in Northern Tallinn in Estonia. The team conducted 14 interviews with 14 representatives of enterprises active in creative and cultural industries (e.g. music, video and books) between November 2020 and April 2021 (total length of interviews: 793 minutes). The interviews were transcribed and analysed by the UTARTU team. Based on the results of the analysis, the team wrote an interim report (deliverable D4.8) and submitted this according to the schedule on M18. The interim report seeks to explain the role of creative hubs (representing agglomeration in creative and cultural industries) on the one hand in digitalisation and on the other hand in the mutual contact, exchange of information, and collaboration in creative and cultural industries. It does that in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic that has had a considerable impact on the strongly agglomerating creative and cultural enterprises. The interim report is a result of numerous discussions of the main results, the structure of the report and methodology, as well as the feedback of peer-reviewers, which have all contributed to improvements during three internal rounds of revisions. The report serves as an input for two next deliverables of *reCreating Europe*: (1) D4.5 Report on newly emerging business models in the creative industries in the wake of increasing digitalisation, paying particular attention to their intellectual property considerations (M30, led by UTARTU), and (2) D4.9 final report on entrepreneurship patterns of creative industries in gentrifying urban neighbourhoods (M36, led by UTARTU) where the ongoing work includes agreements on the next steps in data analysis, the initial structure of the final report and a preliminary plan of activities for M19-M36.

Task 4.3 *Developing best practice codes for creative audiovisual re-use* [M1-M36; Lead partner: UGLA-CREATE. Contributor: UvA-IViR]

Task 4.3 conducted legal research on exceptions and limitations in the UK and the Netherlands, and organised and delivered four online deliberative workshops aimed at identifying the copyright issues and concerns faced by documentary filmmakers and curators of immersive experiences in the two jurisdictions under consideration. UGLA-CREATE was in charge of ethical clearance, research design, project management, desk research on UK exceptions, and the organisation and delivery of the two online workshops with UK filmmakers and curators. UvA-IViR led the same activities in the Netherlands, also conducting desk research on exceptions and organising and delivering two online workshops with Dutch filmmakers and curators. The workshops held in the UK were granted ethical approval by the University of Glasgow: participants received a Participant Information Sheet and signed a Consent Form and Privacy Notice before attending the workshop. UGLA-CREATE researchers conducted desk research on copyright exceptions and other provisions of UK copyright law that are relevant for the reuse of existing materials by documentary filmmakers and curators of immersive experiences. Research methods were designed in consultation with Professor Peter Jaszi, member of the External Expert Advisory Board of *ReCreating Europe* who started the Codes of Best Practices in Fair Use initiative in the United States; and also with researchers from the London School of Economics, the University of Kent and City, University of London who had previous experience of designing deliberative exercises. Potential workshop participants were identified through desk research, the researchers' networks of contacts and existing community networks. The workshops were video-recorded and the recordings were transcribed by the researchers. The researchers then edited the transcripts and coded the data using coding frameworks developed by the participants themselves during the workshops. The findings of these exercises have been systematised in four issue reports: D4.10 'Issue reports on how copyright exceptions and other permitted uses that are relevant for documentary filmmakers and immersive digital heritage practitioners are understood in the Netherlands and the UK'. Researchers from UGLA-CREATE and UvA-IViR drafted the issue reports and legal frameworks of their corresponding jurisdictions and collated them into D4.10. The researchers also engaged with relevant stakeholders in various occasions. For example,

they participated in several meetings of the Screen Heritage Working Group of the UK Feature Docs initiative; and acted as respondents to the CREATE Public Lecture 'An Empirical Perspective on Drafting Copyright Exceptions' by Dr Emily Hudson (24 March 2021) and in the online webinar Building Copyright Literacy for a Global Community of Open Educators with the Code of Best Practice in Fair Use for OER (11 June 2021).

Task 4.4 Copyright User: Designing the EU Copyright Guidance Portal [M1-M36; Lead partner: UGLA-CREATE. Contributors: cross-cutting]

Task 4.4. has focused on outlining the information architecture, navigation and the basic structure of the user interface of the new EU Copyright User Portal. UGLA-CREATE adopted a bottom-up research approach aimed at identifying the copyright knowledge needs of copyright users within the five groups of key stakeholders targeted by *ReCreating Europe*. Specific knowledge needs within these groups have been identified by liaising with partners, researchers and key stakeholders across the *ReCreating Europe* consortium. Through collaboration with Task 4.4 of WP4, the surveys conducted by WP2 and WP5 with academics and GLAMs respectively have included questions aimed at assessing the type and level of knowledge of copyright law of these groups and the topics on which they would like to receive guidance and training. In parallel, UGLA-CREATE conducted a mapping exercise of *ReCreating Europe* work packages to identify the deliverables that might be linked to from CopyrightUser.EU or could inform some of its components. UGLA-CREATE also developed a beta version of an interactive map for the CREATE Copyright in Digital Single Market Directive implementation resource, with a view to expanding the map to visualise the database on copyright flexibilities being developed for D2.3. Primary and secondary navigation of the new portal have also been informed by an analysis of web analytics of the already existing CopyrightUser.org website. The results of these exercises have informed the first version of the information architecture of Copyright User.EU, which can be found in D4.12 'Interim report on the information architecture of the Copyright User EU site'. UGLA-CREATE also developed the brand identity of CopyrightUser.EU, including the main logo of the website.

1.2.5 Work Package 5 – Galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) [M1-M36; WP Leader: UNITN]

Pursuing the objectives illustrated in the GA, the activities of WP5 have focused on the comparative cross-national mapping of the normative context for IPR within the cultural heritage institutions, especially investigating the degree of national transposition of EU law. WP5 is working towards the enhanced understanding of the consequences of digitisation and the implementation of the DMS on cultural diversity, access to culture, and creation of cultural value in the GLAM sector. At the same time, the work of WP5 has also begun to address the issue of contextualising IPRs in place-making. On top and beyond the activities under the different tasks, UNITN - often in partnership with UGLA-CREATE and USZ - organised and participated in conferences and webinars on project-related issues; submitting papers/posters proposals and presenting those during online events, including the Europeana 2020 panel (in which researchers from UNITN, UGLA-CREATE and USZ presented while researchers from SSSA were involved in the preparation of the event) aimed at GLAM stakeholders and other interested parties in November 2020 and the CDSM workshop in June 2021 (in which researchers from UNITN, SSSA, UGLA-CREATE and USZ personally presented). Additionally, all partners involved in the WP participated regularly to WP5 meetings.

Task 5.1 European legal framework for GLAM industries: from closure to Openness [M1-M36; Lead partner: SSSA. Contributors: UNITN, USZ]

The work of Task 5.1 has been focusing on subtask 5.1.1, led by UNITN, on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM), conducting the mapping for GM industries, while SSSA led the parallel subtask 5.1.2, both with the contribution of USZ. The analysis of the legal framework resulted in the delivery of D5.1 (Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU) and D5.2 (Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU). For both subtasks, the existing European legal framework regulating digitized and digital-born content was mapped having regard to national provisions, by means of literature review and online surveys involving national experts from all the

EU Member States. SSSA, leading the subtask 5.1.2, coordinated the activities pursuing the first deliverable D5.2, to which UNITN and USZ contributed, e.g. by providing data and reviewing the sections/parts of the document based on their expertise. Vice versa, UNITN coordinated the research towards D5.1 and expressly involved SSSA and USZ in the compilation (providing theoretical and empirical data) and pre-review of the deliverable.

Task 5.2 Implementation of legal requirements and criteria for Openness by GLAM industries [M5-M30; Lead partner: UNITN. Contributors: SSSA, UGLA-CREAtE, USZ, LIBER, NUIM]

Work for Task 5.2 has so far included the preparation and delivery of GLAM survey (incl. web-platform for the questionnaire, accompanying texts and privacy notes), and the analysis of related data, the preparation of (including privacy information and consent forms) and holding of interviews targeting selected GLAM stakeholders and the subsequent data analysis, in order to proceed to the draft of preliminary reports, under T5.2. The actual response rate for the questionnaire was higher than expected (originally envisioned between 30 and 50 responses in total, covering 8 to 10 European countries). SSSA, UGLA-CREAtE, USZ, LIBER, NUIM contributed to design and review the online survey, e.g. by discussing and suggesting additional questions and then participating to the preliminary analysis of data (some outputs were shared and presented during the events mentioned at the beginning of this section).

Across T5.2 and T5.3, following the questionnaire, a sample of semi-structured interviews have been conducted with selected stakeholders to address specific and controversial issues that emerged from the preliminary analysis of the data gathered from the questionnaire, which served as a basis for D5.4 (Guidelines & FAQs (LA) industries - Interim version) led by LIBER, that prompted the activities under **Task 5.3 Valuing and engaging in Openness with GLAM [M18-M36; Lead partner: UNITN. Contributors: SSSA, USZ, LIBER]**. Such activities will continue in the upcoming months from M18 onwards, and D5.3, under the same task T5.3, but focusing on GM industries, will be delivered in M24. SSSA, USZ and LIBER participated to the preparation of the interviews (e.g. by reviewing the questions and suggesting adjustments) and are all currently involved in the organisation of the first milestone event scheduled for October 2021.

Task 5.4 Digitisation and IPRs in EU place-making [M1-M36, Lead partner: UGLA-CREAtE. Contributors: TARTU, UNITN]

Work has been conducted towards deliverables D5.9 and D5.10. This has included ongoing communication regarding the place-making task by email and video call and including desk-research, sharing and amending scoping papers and offering contributions from law, geography and other perspectives where the teams have expertise, as well as ongoing work in the identification of stakeholders. The work undertaken so far has consisted of work including mapping, reading and integration of legislation and case law, law and geography literature etc. and writing the preparatory content for the deliverables to provide context for the law and geography aspects of IPRs in EU place-making relating broadly to (i) cultural heritage digitisation and circulation and (ii) city branding.

Work has included the identification of the scope of the place-making and intellectual property literature as well as its substantial gaps while building on past research. Research has been undertaken into to specific cities especially Glasgow but embedded in the study of European cities more generally as well as the theoretical literature on, for example, the “creative city”. Through the identification of new sources – from law, geography especially – partners have also considered new areas such as COVID-19 and digital museums, impact of social media, fan tourism, and world heritage bids. UGLA-CREAtE has prepared a detailed Annotated Bibliography and undertaken the desk research to enable the writing of the deliverable sections including on the impact on GLAMs of the new CDSMD and identified relevant projects to place-making. The partners have also undertaken some trademark register searches in the UK, Estonia and Italy for city-related signs. There were also team meetings to share ideas and research.

1.2.6 Work Package 6 – Intermediaries (Copyright Content Moderation and Removal at Scale in the Digital Single Market: What Impact on Access to Culture?) [M1-M33; WP Leader: UvA-IViR]

WP6 and its Tasks last from M1 to M33 of the project. The work is coordinated by UvA and is successfully implemented as a result of an active involvement all project WP members: HIIG, USZ and UCPH. All WP6 tasks and objectives planned for M1-M18 have been accomplished and all deliverables of the period have been submitted, according to the amended and approved Grant Agreement (e.g. moving D.6.2 from M16 to M.21). Progress is assessed in regular plenary meetings between members (at least once every 1.5 months) and frequent side meetings between some of its members for specific tasks. More generally within the project, status and deviations of the objectives have been regularly assessed in the periodic General Assembly (GA) and Project Management Board (PMB) meetings. Beyond what is stated in the amended Grant Agreement, there are no major deviations in terms of use of resources in this reporting period.

WP6 carries out interdisciplinary research to critically examine the impact on digital access to culture and the creation of cultural value of (existing and proposed) legal rules and practices regarding content moderation and removal on variously sized UGC platforms in the DSM. It aims to map, evaluate and measure how such rules and practices affect digital access to culture and the creation of cultural value. In particular, the objectives of WP6 are to: (1) explain and evaluate the existing legal frameworks (both public and private, existing and proposed) that shape the role of intermediaries in organising the circulation of culture and creative works in Europe, including regarding copyright content moderation; (2) explain, critically examine and evaluate the existing practices and technologies that intermediaries deploy to organise the circulation of culture and creative works in Europe, including regarding copyright content moderation; (3) measure the impact of legal frameworks, business practices and technologies on access and diversity, the creation of culture value, and on creators' creative practices and users' consumption patterns; (4) explain and evaluate how the legislative framework conditions shape private models for copyright content moderation.

In the context of WP6, the period M1-M18 involved the performing of Tasks T.6.1 (and respective subtasks) and T.6.2, Deliverable D.6.1 and Milestone MS1. In essence, this corresponds to the Mapping stage of WP6. All work on each task is further described below.

Task 6.1 *Mapping the regulatory framework public/private* [M1-M18; Leader: UvA-IViR. Contributors: USZ, HIIG, UCPH]

T.6.1 carries out an EU and cross-national mapping of public and private ordering sources/measures, legal rules and contractual terms having an impact on content moderation and removal rules and policies, and their effect on digital access to culture and the creation of cultural value. T.6.1 is comprised of 3 subtasks: T6.1.1 EU Level Mapping; T6.1.2 Comparative National Level Mapping; and T6.1.3 Private Regulations by Platforms: ToS, Community Guidelines. The first deliverable from the research in T.6.1 and its subtasks was D.6.1. Interim report on mapping of EU legal framework and intermediaries' practices on copyright content moderation and removal. A final mapping report building on this interim report will conclude the work on T.6.1.

What follows is a general description of division of work in T6.1. For each subtask, see further details below.

UvA-IViR was responsible for coordinating work on all tasks, including procedurally (setting up meetings, documentation, articulation with PMB, GA and WP7, taking the lead and organising workshop MS1) and substantively, including taking the lead in conceptualizing the joint work and reports, and the integration of tasks. UvA-IViR was also primarily responsible for work on T6.1.1, jointly responsible for work on T.6.1.2 (with USZ), and assisted in work on T6.1.3 and T6.2 (led by HIIG). USZ was in charge (jointly with UvA-IViR) and the primary responsible for the work in T6.1.2, as well as involved in providing feedback in T6.1.1 and T.6.1.3. HIIG was responsible for work in T.6.1.3 and T.6.2, as well as providing feedback on T.6.1.1 and T.6.2 UCPH was involved in providing detailed feedback on all aspects of all tasks in M1-M18, even considering its official

work on the project was only scheduled to start in M18. All partners were regularly involved in attending meetings, providing feedback to each other's methods and research, as well as in outreach and dissemination. They were also all involved in drafting D.6.1.

As regards D.6.1 the allocation of work mirrored the work in the tasks. In particular, UvA-IViR was in charge of drafting and conceptualizing the document, as well as organising the work, and incorporating the different contributions from the partners into a final version. UvA-IViR took the lead in writing the following chapter of D.6.1.: Introduction and Outline (1); Conceptual Framework, Methodology and Methods (2); Legal Mapping at EU Level (3); Conclusions Interim Report and Next Steps (6). USZ took the lead in writing the chapter on Legal Mapping at National Level: Comparative Analysis (4), and contributed to chapters 2, 3 and 6. HIG took the lead in writing the chapter Longitudinal Mapping of Online Platforms' Structures of Copyright Content Moderation (5), and contributed to chapters 2 and 6. UCPH contributed significantly to drafting Chapters 2, 3 and 6, and provided detailed feedback on all remaining chapters.

T6.1.1 EU Level Mapping (Leader: UvA-IViR. Contributors: USZ, UCPH). The aim of this subtask is to coherently map the extant legal framework and CJEU interpretation thereof, relevant proposed legislative instruments at EU level and non-binding EU acts. This is complemented by an examination of relevant policy documents and scholarship on the selected legal provisions and topics. As part of this task we have carried out a legal mapping of the topic of this report at EU level. The main focus of our analysis was the legal regime of art. 17 CDSM. To explain this complex provision and its implications, we first provide some context on the legal regime that precedes the CDSM Directive, as it relates to content moderation, including the complex intersection between primary liability (under art. 3 InfoSoc Directive) and arts. 14 and 15 e-Commerce Directive. We then examined the legislative process leading to the adoption of the CDSM Directive, the legal regime of art. 17, the European Commission's stakeholder consultations and Guidance on art. 17 (published only on M18), and the action for annulment of art. 17 initiated by the Polish government in Case C-401/19 (AG Opinion postponed to M19). The focus of our work is a detailed analysis of art. 17, with an emphasis on its liability regime and rules with implication for copyright content moderation by OCSSPs (Online Content Sharing Service Providers), as well as an examination of its interface with the Digital Services Act proposal (which *inter alia* replaces key provisions of the e-Commerce Directive and offers the first legal definition of "content moderation" in EU law). The work in this sub-task was led and carried out by UvA-IViR, in close cooperation with UCPH and USZ, and with feedback from HIG as regards empirical aspects. The writing of Chapters 2 and 3 in D.6.1. in the parts that correspond to this sub-task was done UvA-IViR, in some points in co-authorship with UCPH (see D.6.1 for further details).

In the context of this research, members of the Team, in particular from UvA-IViR and UCPH, have been among the most influential academics in shaping the academic and policy debates on art. 17, as attested by numerous publications and speaking engagements at EU and national levels.

T6.1.2 Comparative National Level Mapping (Leader: USZ. Contributors: UvA-IViR). The aim of this subtask is to carry out comparative legal research on moderation and removal of copyright-protected content in select EU jurisdictions. The main methodological tools for this research are the legal questionnaires for the selected jurisdictions and interviews with national experts. In this context, the first phase of a two-phase questionnaire on the comparative analysis of 10 selected Member States' legal status quo related to the regulation of platform liability in the pre-CDSM Directive implementation period was carried out. As a part of the work, the team (lead by USZ with the close collaboration of UvA-IViR) developed the methodology of the comparative research, drafted the first-phase questionnaire, contacted and selected the national reporters, and analysed the responses of the national reporters. The comparative analysis has evidenced similarities and differences of the national legal systems of 10 EU Member States. The analysis (carried out by USZ and reviewed by UvA) has addressed the direct and indirect liability of intermediaries, and end-users' liability in the pre-CDSM landscape. It also tracked the implementation experiences of the Member States related to art. 17 CDSM. The collected data highlighted similar and remarkably different doctrinal and practical issues present in the Member States legal systems. These differences necessarily mean that the implementation of art. 17 CDSM will pose significantly different challenges for the Member States, which can

ultimately challenge the effectiveness of the newly introduced regime. The second phase of the comparative research will be carried out in the second part of the *reCreating Europe* project, focusing on the implementation and practical functioning of national acts implementing Art.17 CDSM in the selected Member States. Additional details about methodology and content can be derived from D.6.1, especially chapters 2 and 4. In this context, USZ had the responsibility of drafting Chapter 4, which reflects the content of this sub-task, whereas UvA-IViR helped with its conceptualization and review.

T6.1.3 Private Regulations by Platforms: ToS, Community Guidelines (Leader: HIIG). As part of this comprehensive mapping of public and private regulations, HIIG has in task T.6.1.3 collected a diverse and longitudinal set of platform policies and analysed them with regard to copyright questions and to the handling of creative work more broadly. For this work, HIIG collected the Terms of Service, community guidelines, privacy policies, copyright policies and other related public material (such as help pages) of five mainstream platforms (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, Sound Cloud), five decentralized platforms (Diaspora, Mastodon, DTube, Pixelfed, Audius) and five specialized niche platforms (Github, Vimeo, FanFiction, Dribbble, Pornhub). As a spin-off-project, these collected research data are step by step released as open research data under the umbrella of the “Platform Governance Archive” (<https://pga.hiig.de>) to enable future research on the role and governance of intermediaries. The general analysis by HIIG of these private forms of copyright regulation on all platforms and detailed case studies on Facebook and Diaspora have resulted in four major learnings: (1) platforms’ copyright content moderation rules became more complex over time; (2) the platforms’ role became more important in these rules – but discursive focus remained on users; (3) copyright content moderation lost preponderance, with an increasing share of indirect rules and an integration into the quickly widening landscape of content moderation and private regulation by platforms; (4) forms of private regulation are not determined by public regulation nor are their changes; stark differences between mainstream and alternative platforms are probably a result of differing public pressure and politicization. Detailed results have been included in the submitted D6.1 (see chapter 5, drafted by HIIG and revised by UvA) and will be part of D6.2 (in preparation for submission in M21). As noted, the work in this sub-task was led and carried out by HIIG. UvA contributed throughout with feedback on methods and content. All other parts also contributed with feedback on these aspects during plenary meetings, information exchanges and reviews of drafts.

Task 6.2 *Mapping the Current Practices of Copyright Content Moderation and Removal at Scale on Platforms* [M1-M21; Lead partner: HIIG]. In task 6.2, HIIG has investigated the current practices and structures of copyright content moderation and removal on key platforms for sharing and using creative and cultural works with a specific focus in technical measures and the automation copyright content moderation. In case studies, HIIG has investigated the leading technologies and systems deployed by social media platform: ContentID, Rights Manager, and Audible Magic. While existing research typically focusses on trying to understand and surface the hidden logics of the filtering and matching technologies, we have taken a broader perspective that reconstructs the powerful organizational process these systems are embedded in: starting with the registration process for creators and content and their often high entry thresholds; the integrated matching process for content; the business rules applied to content, and the availability and specifics of dispute process. Preliminary results show that the power and impact of these structures and automated mechanisms reside much more in this integration of diverse procedural steps than in specifics of their filter and matching technologies. HIIG and the remaining partners assume that these “algorithmic systems” and their increasing pertinence do indeed have impact on cultural diversity and creativity (cf. upcoming Task T.6.3). Detailed results will be part of D6.2 (M21).

Task 6.3 *Evaluating Legal Frameworks on the Different Levels (EU vs. national, public vs. private)* [M18-M30; Lead partners: CPH, UvA-IViR; Contributors: USZ] and Task 6.4 *Measuring the impact of moderation practices and technologies on access and diversity* [M18-M30; Lead partner: HIIG] have just started and the related roadmaps are under planning.

1.2.7 Work Package 7 – Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach [M1-M36; WP Leader: LIBER]

1.2.7.1 WP7 Summary

How does the work carried out contribute to WP objectives?

WP7 runs horizontally within the project with the following main objectives:

- Produce a sound KPI-driven ‘Engagement and Outreach Strategy’ for the involvement of stakeholders that are relevant for the project, including beyond the key categories covered by the vertical WPs (End users, Creative industries, GLAM and Intermediaries). The Strategy aims to expand the project’s network, illustrate ways to engage the highest number of stakeholders in the discussion, and follow up on engagement activities. All activities will be measured against a set of KPIs and revisited half-way through the project.
- Disseminate the project’s activities, training materials, guidelines/FAQ, best practices, policy recommendations, reports and other results to relevant stakeholders and the broader public, having as the main entry point for interaction the project’s website and stakeholders’ platform, with the aim to ensure the broadest possible audience for the project’s initiatives and to increase initiative impact.
- Adopt the project’s best practices, produced by the vertical WPs (2-6) and by the key target stakeholder groups.
- Create targeted communication materials and to run and support some of the project’s events.
- Develop the Training Toolkit as an element of the website and its stakeholders’ platform, which will be initially populated with training material and learning materials created by vertical WPs, and then enriched with materials created and shared by stakeholders (‘train-the-trainer’ approach).

WP7 main results in M1-M18

- Capturing and analysing the current landscape and stakeholder basis of the project;
- Creating the overall project branding identity and templates;
- Producing the Engagement and Outreach Strategy of the project, including supporting guidance and monitoring mechanisms and tools;
- Creating a framework for building expertise;
- Kick-starting two-way communication of the project at an early stage, based on close collaboration with all other WPs, supporting them horizontally in engaging with key and secondary stakeholders, monitoring the levels of engagement and outreach, while aiming at maximizing impact;
- Promoting and supporting several vertical activities targeting key stakeholders and maximising their impact.
- Presenting in several third-party events;
- Writing several blogposts and other communication items outside of *reCreating Europe’s* website.

Additional outputs or unplanned actions (further details below):

- Signing a Memorandum of Understanding with InDICES;
- Participation in the Horizon Results Booster;
- Establishing a partnership with COMMUNIA within the framework of WP2 activities on copyright flexibilities;
- Addressing an open letter to the European Commission concerning the right of revocation;
- Running an online campaign for World IP day 2021;
- Promoting and supporting a flagship online Conference on CDSM Directive implementation;
- Having 3 Project-dedicated pages on partners' websites (LIBER, UNITN, UCPH)

List of Milestones achieved in RP1

- MS2 – Stakeholder Landscape Analysis (M4);
- MS4 – Expertise Building Framework (M12);
- MS8 – Evaluation of Engagement Strategy (M18).

List of Deliverables submitted in RP1

- D7.1 - Engagement and Outreach Strategy (M6);
- D7.2 - Project's brand identity, communication kit and website (M2).

1.2.7.2 WP7 Progress

Task 7.1 Analysis of stakeholder landscape, Engagement and Outreach activities [M1-M36; Lead partner: LIBER. Contributors: SSSA, UNITN, UvA-IViR, UGLA-CREATe, NUIM]

Subtask 7.1.1 Analysis of stakeholder landscape and general engagement strategy. [Lead partner: LIBER. Contributors: SSSA, UNITN, UvA-IViR, UGLA-CREATe, NUIM]

During the 1st period of the project (M1-M18), WP7 performed the initial analysis of the stakeholder landscape to allow the start of communication and engagement activities of the project as soon as possible. Related work is described in detail in MS2 – Stakeholder Landscape Analysis. The analysis was based on a mapping exercise, in which all project partners participated, and currently serves as an internal, ever-growing database of stakeholders and related information for engagement and outreach activities. The Stakeholder Landscape Analysis included a) a short description per key stakeholder group, b) the main stakeholder analysis based on the mapping exercise, c) a snapshot of the Engagement and Outreach Strategy. Further to key stakeholder groups targeted by the project, the analysis also took into consideration other stakeholder categories not directly targeted by the project, such as funders, policymakers, institutions, pertinent projects, relevant initiatives, and the general public. The aim of the initial analysis and periodically updated stakeholder database was not only to identify the existing stakeholder basis of the project - including connections, channels and tools that are already in place - but also to be used as a tool for further expansion and monitoring across set KPIs.

D7.1 - Engagement and Outreach Strategy was delivered in M6. This deliverable represents a sound and KPI-driven strategy, following a multi-disciplinary and stakeholder-centric approach, which outlines the activities to be followed and tools to be used in terms of engagement, outreach and building expertise throughout the project. It also sets up and fosters two-way interaction, encourages input from stakeholders, addresses awareness gaps and maximises the impact of the project, while adapting to challenges. The strategy describes the main communication and engagement channels that the project will be using, including:

- *reCreating Europe* website;
- *reCreating Europe* stakeholders' platform;
- Training materials, toolkit and events;
- Conference(s);
- Workshops and focus groups;
- Participatory research tools (questionnaires, surveys and interviews);
- Best practices;
- Case studies;
- Webinars;
- Social media;
- Third-party events and conferences;
- Newsletter;
- Information and communication materials;
- Scientific publications;
- Blogposts;
- Videos and dedicated YouTube channel.

Based on the initial analysis, the Engagement and Outreach Strategy describes a) the landscape, b) key messages, c) main communication and engagement channels and d) specific target activities the project will be using and implementing per key stakeholder category. It also provides and details the communication and dissemination plan based on S.M.A.R.T. (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time bound) communication objectives and specific KPIs, which are regularly monitored and periodically evaluated and updated. To support the implementation and monitoring of communication and engagement activities, the Strategy was complemented by guiding documentation:

- Dissemination and Outreach Checklist;
- Dissemination, Engagement and Training Activities Tracker;
- Guidelines for post-event blog post and report writing;
- Blog post schedule;
- Social media content feeder;
- Social media rotation schedule

The Strategy included a provision for training, expected impact and risk assessment, including the COVID-19 pandemic-associated risk, specifically because the first wave of the pandemic took place when the Strategy was delivered.

As provisioned, WP7 delivered *MS8 – Evaluation of Engagement Strategy* in M18. The evaluation started with providing the state of the art per key stakeholder group, as well as a planning table including delivered and upcoming engagement and dissemination activities. The verification process used several measures, such as verifying and validating the engagement and outreach activities with the *reCreating Europe* partners regularly and at three different levels (WP7, PMB and GA), regularly collecting information and updates, checking across KPIs, taking into consideration the COVID-19 pandemic repercussions and Amendment No AMD-870626-3, relevant documentation and input provided by all WP partners.

Subtask 7.1.2 Branding, communication kit, website development and the stakeholders' platform [Lead partner: SSSA. Contributor: LIBER]

WP7 delivered *D7.2 - Project's brand identity, communication kit and website* in M2, which determined the project's brand identity and provided communication material available to the whole consortium. The items included were:

- Project logo
- PowerPoint template and standard project presentation
- Brochure template
- Poster template
- Introductory video and related intro and end slides
- Project website
- Deliverable template
- Letterhead

The abovementioned materials are reviewed periodically, and iterations are taking place (e.g. Project's website). Further communication collaterals were produced for the needs of RP1 (see Table 1.2.7.2 – Overall communication collaterals produced in RP1).

Figure 1.2.7.1 Examples of the *reCreating Europe* Newsletter

View this email in your browser

ReCreating Europe

ReCreating Europe | Newsletter | March 2021

Hello! We're glad you're here. This second ReCreating Europe Newsletter is delivered to you because you've signed up for news and updates about the project. This second newsletter comes out on the cusp of spring - and we're happy to mention that this brings many exciting events during the coming months.

Hence, we're looking forward to sharing the outcomes of our work with you. Hopefully, the time to meet face-to-face will soon be part of our reality again.

Best wishes and stay healthy!

New collaboration

EU Copyright Collaboration

We are happy to announce a collaboration with [COMPTONIA](#) within the frame of the legal mapping of copyright flexibilities in the EU and the 27 Member States. This collaboration represents a unique occasion for bringing the research on European copyright exceptions and limitations up to the next level. Find more about it here: <https://bit.ly/2Qzrv6W>

Future events

The University of Szeged, a member of the reCreating Europe consortium, in collaboration with the Pázmány Péter Catholic University will host the **Fifth Annual Workshop on Intellectual Property Rights in Szeged (WIPS)** on **April 19-20, 2021**. The virtual gathering of 40 speakers and 100+ attendees will offer an insight into the work of several reCreating Europe researchers. [More information here.](#)

CREATE

CREATE and reCreating Europe are delighted to announce that Emily Hudson will be delivering our third public lecture of this academic year. Due to Covid-19 lockdown restrictions which remain in place, this event will be hosted online.

[An Empirical Perspective on Drafting Copyright Exceptions](#)

Speaker: Emily Hudson
Date: Wednesday 24 March 17:30-19:00 GMT

Past events

In February, three members of the ReCreating Europe have given public

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ReCreating Europe

ReCreating Europe | Newsletter | December 2020

Hello! We're glad you're here. This first ReCreating Europe Newsletter is delivered to you because you've signed up for news and updates about the project. This first newsletter comes out at the very last month of a year that has been challenging in many ways for every one of us. Despite these challenging times, ReCreating Europe has been very active, so we hope you will enjoy this summary before jumping in 2021 with us!

Best wishes for these festive holidays and most importantly, stay safe & well.

Project news

A survey on copyright law & open policies

ReCreating Europe has launched a survey to analyse the impact of copyright law and open policies in relation to digitisation in the GLAM sector. The objective is to determine whether Galleries Libraries Archives Museums (GLAMs) are aligned with legal restrictions on digitisation and to what extent legal and technological measures are applied. If you haven't yet please [fill up the survey](#) which is [opened until the 31st of December 2020](#).

An open letter to the European Commission

ReCreating Europe is among a group of leading international academics who have published an open letter to the European Commission concerning the right of revocation. This new right, regulating copyright contracts, is provided for in article 22 of the recent [EU Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market](#). Find more about it [here](#).

Europeana conference 2020

Members of the ReCreating Europe took part in the online [Europeana 2020 conference](#). This was an opportunity provide a general overview of the aims and activities of the whole project, to allow participants to test the ReCreating Europe GLAM survey, and to offer a first basic training on some of the most relevant legal aspects related to digitisation in the GLAM sector. You can watch the presentations on the [ReCreating Europe YouTube channel](#)

Subtask 7.1.3 Engagement with the key stakeholder categories [Lead partner: LIBER. Contributors: SSSA, UNITN, UvA-IViR, UGLA-CREAtE]

Engagement and outreach highlights for RP1

- The project [Signed a Memorandum of Understanding with InDICES](#), a project funded by the same call, ensuring synergies and alignment when possible;
- *ReCreating Europe* launched [a public survey to analyse the impact of copyright law and open policies in relation to digitisation in the GLAM sector](#) in the context of WP5. The survey ran from September 2020 to January 2021 and reached 286 participants.
- The project addressed an [Open letter to the European Commission concerning the right of revocation](#) on December 11th 2020;
- The project announced it would be [joining forces with COMMUNIA on European Copyright exceptions and limitation](#) in the context of WP2;
- *ReCreating Europe* publicly celebrated World IP Day 2021 through an [online campaign](#) on April 25th 2021;

Figure 1.2.7.2 Virtual banner of the *reCreating Europe* campaign on World IP Day 2021

- *ReCreating Europe* hosted an [online Conference on CDSM Directive implementation](#) on June 21st 2021, as an initiative of SSSA under WP1 organized to present the interim research results achieved under WP2, WP3, WP5 and WP6, and discuss them with representatives of key stakeholders (authors and/or performers, creative industries, end users, galleries, libraries, archives and/or museums, and intermediaries), who acted as respondents. The conference was broadly attended (214 people, whilst being live-streamed on YouTube) and generated extreme interest towards the project.
- Partners created 3 project-dedicated pages on their websites to further boost communication to dedicated key stakeholders ([LIBER](#), [UNITN](#), [UCPH](#));
- *ReCreating Europe* joined the [Horizon Results Booster](#) with the aim of boosting dissemination of the project and enhancing impact by leveraging synergies with relevant projects;
- In RP1 the project delivered and disseminated [12 reports](#) and 1 set of [guidelines and FAQs](#).

A summary of dissemination activities is presented in Table 1.2.7.3, while an estimation of reached stakeholders for the period is presented in Table 1.2.7.1. The following rules have been used:

- Official *reCreating Europe* social media impressions are reported under general public;
- In the case of individual partners' social media impressions, taking into consideration the fact that specific partners act as outreach champions, 1/3 were reported under the stakeholder group targeted by the relevant WP and stakeholder, and 2/3 were reported under general public;

- For social media posts, where impressions could not be retrieved, the number of followers was used for the estimation;
- In the case of blogposts/non-peer reviewed publications the number of downloads were reported under the stakeholder group of the respective WP, while the views were reported under the general public;
- Numbers related to activities targeting a specific audience (e.g. a video targeting WP2), were reported under the specific stakeholder group, unless we have an evidence that suggests otherwise;
- For events that no specific estimation of break-down per stakeholder group could be provided, the numbers are reported under general public. Accordingly, for activities reported that no estimation of audience could be provided, the activities are counted, but no reach has been reported (e.g. in cases of participation with a presentation in third-party events).

Figure 1.2.7.3. Visual Overview of reCreating Europe’s Social Media Accounts (January 2021 – June 2021)

Task 7.2 Expertise Building and Training Toolkit [M6-M36; Lead partner: LIBER. Contributors: SSSA, UNITN, UvA-IViR, UGLA-CREaTe, NUIM]

WP7 delivered *MS4 – Expertise Building Framework* in M12. The Expertise Building Framework depicts the strategic goals, structure, description of content, tools and timeline of *reCreating Europe*'s building expertise activities. An important element of its methodology is following a train-the-trainer approach and FAIR principles. The framework maps the project's training activities and materials per key stakeholder category and provides an activity plan with a tentative timetable, which is used in the implementation and monitoring of relevant activities. It provides preliminary information on the upcoming Training Toolkit, as well as a risks assessment and mitigation planning.

Building expertise highlights for RP1

- [*reCreating Europe Webinar: Public and Private Regulatory Framework of Online Intermediaries*](#): the first webinar of the project took place on May 5th 2020 in the context of WP6 targeting intermediaries and gathered a total of 83 attendees and 230 views on YouTube;
- [*ReCreating Europe Workshop: The State of Exceptions & Limitations: Copyright Flexibilities in the EU & Member States*](#): This building expertise event took place online on June 1st 2021, in the context of WP2 targeting end users and gathered a total of 117 attendees.
- A Seminar "[*The reproduction of works of visual arts in the public domain and the implementation of the Digital Single Market Directive. Prospects on the implementation of Article 14 of Directive 2019/790/UE on Copyright in the Digital Single Market*](#)" (in Italian only)" took place on February 10th 2021 and gathered a total of 80 attendees.

1.2.7.3 Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

The project's dissemination, engagement and outreach activities were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic repercussions and consequent delay of several deliverables as per the Amendment to the Grant Agreement. This is visible through the project's reach, which did not grow as fast as originally predicted in the first months of the project. However, through regular monitoring at WP7, PMB and GA levels, as well as strong collaboration and efforts of the consortium, several KPIs have already been achieved, reach is growing exponentially, and *reCreating Europe* is achieving significant impact (see WP7 tables). WP7 has provided monitoring mechanisms and tools for engagement, outreach and building expertise activities, while supporting and promoting the vertical WP activities. Extra activities are even being delivered and/or supported to ensure the maximisation of impact whenever possible.

WP7 Tables 1.2.7.1-7

Table 1.2.7.1 - Key Stakeholders in a nutshell

Stakeholder	Who are they?	Their role	Outreach Champion(s)	Reach in RP1
End users	General public, associations of consumers, specific categories of vulnerable users (people with disabilities, minorities, etc.), related associations and academics	Consumption, access	SSSA, NUIM	30.894
Individual authors and performers	Associations and CMOs of authors and performers in different sectors (mostly organised by discipline, i.e., writers, journalists, actors, directors, photographers etc.), independent non-associated authors and performers	Creation	UvA-IViR	4.481
Creative industries	General public, associations, and creators in audio-visual industries	Creation	UGLA-CREATe, UvA-IViR, SSSA, UTARTU	34.169
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums	Preservation, access, education, research	UNITN, SSSA, LIBER	24.920
Intermediaries	Social media services and online platforms (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Vimeo, etc.)	Distribution, re-use, (UGC), access	UvA-IViR, HIIG	23.257
Other, General public	All other stakeholders targeted by the project, including general public		All	470.643

Table 1.2.7.2 – Overall communication collaterals produced in RP1

Type of item	No	Description of item	Link
Project logo	1	Official <i>reCreating Europe</i> official logo and funding acknowledgment	Annexed in D7.2
PowerPoint template	1	PowerPoint template to be used for project-related presentations	Annexed in D7.2
Standard project presentation	1	Standard overall <i>reCreating Europe</i> presentation	Annexed in D7.2
Brochure template	1	<i>reCreating Europe</i> template for project brochures	Annexed in D7.2
Poster template	1	<i>reCreating Europe</i> template for project posters	Annexed in D7.2
Introductory video and related intro and end slides	2	Official intro and end slides for <i>reCreating Europe</i> videos	Annexed in D7.2

Project website	1	Official <i>reCreating Europe</i> website with 21 landing pages, including 6 pages per stakeholder group for the dedicated stakeholder groups, 6 pages per activity/type of resources, and the stakeholders' platform in private mode (under development)	https://www.recreating.eu/
Deliverable template	1	Template to be used for <i>reCreating Europe</i> deliverables	Annexed in D7.2
Letterhead	1	Letterhead to be used for <i>reCreating Europe</i> official communication	Annexed in D7.2
Newsletter subscription page		Subscription page for the official newsletter on <i>reCreating Europe</i> website	https://www.recreating.eu/newsletter-recreating-europe/
Newsletters in RP1	2	Newsletters sent in RP1	https://mailchi.mp/38f19d1dd882/recreating-europe-newsletter-december-2020 https://mailchi.mp/87c1e0497d43/recreating-europe-newsletter-2-march-2021
YouTube Channel	1	Official <i>reCreating Europe</i> YouTube channel	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCmc6HzXrwyj33f50vFq7u0Q
Videos	22	Promotional videos linked to <i>reCreating Europe</i> work and related events	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCmc6HzXrwyj33f50vFq7u0Q/videos
Social media accounts	3	Official <i>reCreating Europe</i> social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn)	https://www.facebook.com/reCreatingEU https://twitter.com/recreategeu https://www.linkedin.com/company/recreating-europe/
Poster presentation	1	Poster presented at the LIBER2021 online conference	https://zenodo.org/record/4881291#.YPb1CegzY2x

Table 1.2.7.3 - Summary of dissemination activities in RP1

Description	No
Organisation of a Conference	1
Organisation of a Workshop	0
Scientific and/or peer-reviewed publications	28
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	18
Flyer	1
Training	7

Social media posts	530
Website updates	7
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	2
Participation to a Conference	10
Participation to a Workshop	15
Video/Film	23
Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	1
Other	9

Table 1.2.7.4 – Status across KPIs as of June 2021

Outreach and Engagement channels	Target audience	KPI	Measure	Current Stats
ReCreating Europe website	5 Key stakeholder groups (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Project partners Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & initiatives General public	No. of visitors Landing pages	At least 300 unique visitors per month. Each topic will have a dedicated space. There will be separate dedicated areas per stakeholder group.	Number of visitors per month*: June 2020: 110 July 2020: 147 August 2020: 45 September 2020: 136 October 2020: 273 November 2020: 376 December 2020: 312 January 2021: 309 February 2021: 342 March 2021: 720 April 2021: 791 May 2021: 842 June 2021: 1021 (as of 28 June) Landing pages: 6 pages per stakeholder group for the dedicated stakeholder groups 6 pages per activity/type of resources 21 landing pages overall

				*Stats able to be recorded from June 2020 onwards
Traditional and social media	Key stakeholder groups (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & Initiatives General public	No. of Tweets No. of Facebook posts No. of LinkedIn posts No. of Twitter followers No. of Facebook page followers No. of LinkedIn group members No. of YouTube views	> 800 tweets/year (tweeted and retweeted) > 40 Facebook posts/year > 40 LinkedIn posts per year >800 twitter followers from outside the project >300 Facebook page followers >100 LinkedIn page members >100 YouTube views/video 1 introductory video 1 tutorial per key stakeholder category	Total Lifetime Stats (as of 28 June 2021) for <i>reCreating Europe</i> social media: 385 Twitter posts/retweets (80 in 2020) 57 Facebook posts (5 in 2020) 56 LinkedIn posts (5 in 2020) 611 Twitter followers: (195 in 2020) 372 Facebook page 'followers' (298 in 2020) 254 LinkedIn page members (27 in 2020) 36 YouTube followers (5 in 2020) 1 overall introductory video and 7 introductory videos per WP
Communication and information materials	Key stakeholder group (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & Initiatives General public	Number of blog posts/newsletters Number of posters Number of brochures/leaflets Number of conference/workshop collaterals	3 newsletters per year >6 posters during the project >10 brochures/leaflets during the course of the project >10 different items as conference/workshop collaterals	As of 28 June 2021: 1 Newsletter in 2020 1 Newsletter in 2021; 1 scheduled for 15 July 2021 1 poster introductory poster template 1 poster (WP5) presented at LIBER2021 1 introductory brochure template
Workshops/focus groups	Key stakeholder group (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & Initiatives General public	Number of Workshops Number of participants	WP2: 1 workshop for stakeholders (consumer associations, associations representing disadvantaged users) to gather feedback on best practices and validate	The activities under this category are planned, but not delivered yet. However, an engagement online conference has been delivered on 21 June 2021 on the CDSMD implementation: Attendees: 214 (Zoom) approx. 5 (live-stream YouTube)

		<p>results. Expected participants: 50</p> <p>WP4: 2 roundtables with focus groups on territoriality, around 15 participants.</p> <p>WP4: deliberative exercises with documentary filmmakers and immersive digital heritage practitioners</p> <p>WP5: 2 workshops at GLAM premises, or in connection with other relevant conferences (Workshops @ GLAM) involving GLAM stakeholders to gather feedback. Around 50 participants</p> <p>WP5: 2 workshops open to the general public to be held at partners' premises and possibly in connection with a consortium meeting. Around 50 participants</p> <p>WP5: an event held at the EU Parliament premise to address policy makers, but open</p>	
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			to the public. Around 80 participants WP6: 5 Workshops with experts on the legal aspects and platforms practices on content moderation at scale	
Final Conference	Key stakeholder group (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & Initiatives General public	Number of Conferences Number of participants	One Final Conference > 100 expected participants	N/A, activity planned for M35
Scientific publications	Key stakeholder group (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & Initiatives General public	Number of scientific publications	>3 WP2 peer reviewed publications > 3 WP3 open access peer reviewed publications >2 WP4 open access peer reviewed publications (based on reports) >3 WP5 open access peer reviewed publications >3 WP6 peer reviewed publications	As of 28 June 2021: 28 scientific and/or peer-reviewed publications, of which 17 project deliverables and 12 other publications targeting WP2 (2), WP3 (1); WP5 (1); WP6 (7) Further activities under this category are planned, but not delivered yet.
Tools and training material for expertise building	Key stakeholder group (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & initiatives	Number of tools to support expertise building Number of building expertise materials Number of webinars and trainings Number of tutorials	1 Training Toolkit > 1 piece for building expertise/set of guidelines per key stakeholder category > 4 EU copyright guidelines (WP4) and 10x original Explanatory infographics/illustrations	1 set of Guidelines and FAQs for LA industries (interim version) WP6 online workshop: 05.05.2020; 83 attendees, 230 views on YouTube WP5 seminar: 12 October 2020 WP5 seminar: 10 February 2021; 80 attendees WP6 lecture: 16 March 2021 WP5 public lecture: 24 March 2021

	General public		> 1 webinar per key stakeholder category > 1 tutorial per key stakeholder category	WP3 closed workshop: 27 May 2021 WP2 webinar: 01 June 2021; 117 attendees The rest of the activities under this category are planned, but not delivered yet.
Best practices and policy recommendations	Key stakeholder group (end users, authors & performers, creative industries, GLAM, intermediaries) Policy makers Funders Institutions Relevant projects & initiatives General public	Number of guidelines and policy recommendations	1 Code of best practices re: end users and access to culture (WP2) 1 set of policy recommendations for regulators (WP2) > 2 Codes of best practices in relation to copyright in the AV sectors (WP4) 1 set of policy recommendations on territoriality (WP4) > 1 set of policy recommendations and best practices for lawmakers and UGC platforms (WP6, D6.3)	N/A The activities under this category are planned, but not delivered yet.